

INVISIBLE WALLS: WHERE HOME DOESN'T REACH. A CHRONICLE OF RESIDENTIAL EXCLUSION IN SPAIN.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest in the present manuscript, as it is a scientific article of my own authorship, without the involvement of third parties or any funding.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data extracted for the development of this article have been retrieved from databases such as the INE (National Statistics Institute) and publications by the Housing Observatory and the State Agency, as well as from various news reports on the topic of residential exclusion in Spain in recent years.

ETHICAL CODE DATA DECLARATION

The data included in this research do not require consent or approval from third parties.

Furthermore, there are no conflicts of interest under the ethical code, as no third parties are involved or affected, since this is a qualitative study that at no point harms any third parties.

AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, human rights in our country are being violated. Although the Declaration stipulates the right to a decent home, every day hundreds of families are evicted from their homes because they cannot afford to keep paying; many other segments of the population are displaced to the outskirts of cities due to a lack of resources; and still others, tho they have a home, lack the minimum conditions necessary to ensure their well-being or subsistence.

This work seeks to capture how, in Spain, housing—far from being a universal right—has become a luxury that the most vulnerable cannot afford.

KEYWORDS

Human Rights, Residential Exclusion, Evictions, Public Policies

INTRODUCTION.

Housing plays a fundamental role in social organization and serves as a source of social stability in our society. Unfortunately, the housing access conditions imposed by our current residential system have led to an increase in the difficulties people face in meeting their housing needs, thereby increasing the vulnerability of sectors and social groups that were once perfectly integrated (Antón, F. & Cortés, L., 2007). Today, housing problems have spread to a large number of sectors of society, becoming chronic among some groups who cannot meet their housing needs independently (Antón, F. & Cortés, L., 2007).

The hypothesis of this paper is that the current housing model violates the human rights of the vast majority of the Spanish population, hence the need to incorporate these rights into the development of current public policies.

Likewise, this reflection article seeks to examine mortgage foreclosure proceedings in Spain, the role of social policies in the context of the crisis, and, above all, the role of human rights in this context.

2. METHODOLOGY

To prepare this article, an exhaustive information search was conducted: first, an Internet search was carried out, focusing on journalistic and research sources that addressed the topic of the current housing situation in our country. Next, bibliographic

references on the topic were sought, and finally, databases such as the INE were consulted, in an effort to obtain a broad and objective perspective and objective about the phenomenon of residential exclusion and eviction processes in Spain.

During the information selection process, sources that offered a rigorous, serious, and respectful treatment of the topic were chosen, while those of a sensationalist nature were discarded.

Regarding the approach or procedure used to collect and analyze information for the development of this reflection article, a qualitative methodology was employed, based on critical reading and an exhaustive, detailed, and comparative analysis of the selected documents, ensuring a deep understanding and a faithful representation of the issue addressed.

3. RESIDENTIAL EXCLUSION AND HUMAN RIGHTS RESIDENTIAL EXCLUSION AND HUMAN RIGHTS

Housing is a central element in people's lives; it is a fundamental right, like education, healthcare, and social protection, recognized in Article 47 of the Spanish Constitution. It is the place where we learn to relate to others, where our personality is first structured, and where we feel identified with a specific space and territory.

Housing is a fundamental component of each person's social integration process; of course, for this principle to be fulfilled, the housing must meet the necessary physical, amenity (furniture, electricity, water, heating, etc.), and economic characteristics (with costs that align with tenants' income or salary) to ensure an adequate quality of life for its occupants. Otherwise, it can become a vulnerability factor that, combined with other risk factors, can trigger a process of social exclusion (Arriba González, A., 2009), and in this context, I wonder... Is housing a factor of social inclusion or exclusion? Are current public housing policies designed with the current Universal Declaration of Human Rights in mind? Are we free to access decent housing?

Residential exclusion is a permanent and intense phenomenon in today's Spanish society. For people in this situation, housing can become a factor of imbalance and social instability that hinders their social integration (Antón, F. & Cortés, L., 2007). According to Eva Juan (2011):

“The housing problem is a social inequality issue that can be defined as the failure to uphold every individual's right to decent housing, understood as housing that meets the necessary conditions of safety, stability, design, and sanitation, and that enables the

adequate development of the person in all facets and activities, in a broad, comprehensive, and extensive sense” (p. 130).

As we can see, the current residential model excludes the most vulnerable population groups, “displacing” them to the suburbs of cities. Residential exclusion is not limited to the perpetuation of shantytowns and substandard housing; it also manifests in families’ difficulties in accessing better-equipped housing, in overcrowding and overoccupancy of some dwellings, in the concentration and residential segregation in certain towns and cities, and in physical and economic maintenance challenges that sometimes affect public rental housing as well (Antón, F. & Cortés, L., 2007). Indeed, we can affirm that in all these situations the affected individuals suffer a violation of their human rights, which occurs when a social right is turned into a business or a commodity. The current housing system not only condemns the most disadvantaged sectors of the population but also many of its citizens, who, due to rising prices, find their access curtailed unless they accept lifelong debt, since its members are subjected to the rules of the labor market (precarious and poorly paid jobs, job insecurity, etc.), becoming “chained” subjects under the control of an unscrupulous market and a corrupt state, and thus, as Karl Marx (1844) put it, “alienated” subjects.

For Marx (1844), alienation begins with the loss of the essence of the human being, so that one becomes an inert, empty being. Hence the need to incorporate a labor market that guarantees minimum standards for well-being and subsistence. On the other hand, for Locke (1989), labor was how man acquired his property; the problem is that in these times of crisis, labor is neither synonymous with quality of life, nor with rights (precarious contracts and wages), nor with greater opportunities, since in recent years the labor market has been characterized by insecure, unstable, and temporary employment (the now-famous “precariat”), which leads to a loss of status and rights. and workers’ rights (Standing, G., 2014), turning the concepts of work and poverty into complementary ones.

Housing, like healthcare or education, is a right, but it has not been protected in the same way as other rights; it is a “pending right.” Housing facilitates access to other rights, such as employment, healthcare, education, etc. For example, if a person wishes to access the healthcare, education, or labor system, they must have a fixed address, so that all those without a roof over their heads are excluded from enjoying this right (violation of human rights: housing, education, health, etc.).

On the other hand, current public policies leave many people on the sidelines because, in many cases, beneficiaries of these programs must meet such demanding requirements that most of the population is excluded from accessing them—a population that, although not living in a state of total rights violation, experiences daily limitations or infringements on their quality of life.

As recognized by the Commission on Human Settlements and the Global Strategy for Shelter (Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 1992): the concept of “adequate housing” refers to “a place where one can isolate oneself if desired, with adequate space, security, appropriate lighting and ventilation, basic infrastructure, and a suitable location in relation to work and basic services, all at a reasonable cost.” As we can see, the right to adequate housing is much more than simply having a place to live, since such housing must provide individuals with minimum levels of well-being and subsistence (a situation that our current housing system is unable to guarantee).

Likewise, housing can be a key factor in a person’s integration; conversely, lacking housing or living in inadequate conditions can trigger processes of marginalization and social exclusion. Hence the need to take into account the current Declaration of Human Rights in the development of public housing policies, since only by understanding the Right to Housing from a human rights perspective will we be able to achieve just, equitable, and universal policies.

It is important to mention that the absence or scarcity of resources should not justify a democratic state’s failure to fulfill its obligation to oversee the non-enforcement of certain laws, thereby ensuring the observance of human rights.

Today, it is essential in the implementation of current public policies to have processes that integrate a human rights perspective into the development of their programs, with the aim of contributing to the strengthening and well-being of Spanish society.

4. BACKGROUND OF THE PROBLEM

In recent years, our country has been governed by market logic, which has placed economic profit above use value, meaning that each seller sets the price of a good based on maximum profitability, always with an eye on their financial investment. This has led to an overvaluation of housing prices, since during this period the price of a property was determined by the amount of debt each person was willing to take on, resulting in an inflated price that was out of reach for many families. Consequently, most citizens had to

turn to financial institutions for the necessary financing to secure a basic necessity (Alemany, A. and Colau, A., 2012).

Today, our system does not fight to defend human rights but is governed by market rules, in which commercial rights take precedence over human rights, leaving in oblivion all those who are not economically profitable and “displacing” to the outskirts of the city those whom this society has disenfranchised (certain sectors of the population who cannot access the right to decent housing because they lack sufficient financial resources).

The Spanish housing model is contradictory, as housing is recognized as a right both in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Article 25) and in the current Spanish Constitution (Article 47) as a fundamental right; yet every day hundreds of people are evicted from their homes for being unable to continue paying for housing that was unaffordable from the outset. Coupled with the loss of employment by thousands of families, the path to exclusion is often inevitable, and when comparing the price trends of other essential goods with those of housing—relative to the evolution of household income—housing is excessively expensive, becoming a luxury item. “It is necessary to seek measures that address the contradictory reality of an oversupply of housing and its inaccessibility to citizens” (Barriga, L., 2012).

On the other hand, part of the public housing policies was aimed at boosting the production of officially subsidized housing, which is funded by public authorities, in an effort to increase the supply of more affordable homes so that disadvantaged groups could access them. The problem is that in recent years, the creation of subsidized housing has been a lucrative fraud, since the intended beneficiaries cannot afford it due to a lack of financial resources, while those who are not supposed to access it (affluent middle classes) do, resulting in a completely illegal sales and rental business (Arriba González, A., 2009).

Currently, social policies are supposed to promote equality and freedom among the members of the community, but really... Are the rights of the population what determine the choice of which social policies are enacted, or are the hidden interests behind them what dominate the option of free political choice?

When choosing one policy option over another, it is important to consider the magnitude of the problem, since social pressure has led to the implementation of certain policies, such as the Equality Act. Hence the need to raise awareness about the current situation of residential exclusion and housing in our country so that we can change things. It is then that a question arises for democracy: social welfare or private interest? Are

human rights truly universal, or do they instead depend on income level or individuals' economic capacity? Do all the world's inhabitants have the same opportunities to realize these rights?

On the other hand, the absence of social policies prevents the provision of basic services in some peripheral neighborhoods of certain cities, hindering the fulfillment of certain human rights.

It is curious to observe how, in many cities, "hotspots" emerge where residents are characterized by low income levels (economic insecurity, unemployment, etc.), concentrating the most excluded populations (immigrants, Roma, etc.) in specific buildings or areas, as determined by the housing policies that city leaders have allocated to their constituents based on purely esthetic criteria (the "poor" on the outskirts of the city, because "out of sight, out of mind") or economic ones. Does this mean that territorial inequality is linked to unequal protection? What happens as we move on? As we move closer to the peripheries of cities, do opportunities and wellbeing become limited?

According to Julio Alguacil (2006): There is a tendency for the new proletariat (poor immigrants, young people with very low incomes, and those affected by the labor market) to settle and concentrate in the city's most devalued and degraded neighborhoods, where housing is more affordable precisely because of the poor living conditions (distance, isolation, inadequate housing, etc.). (p. 162)

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According to Richard Rorty (1998), this happens when certain people are no longer considered human beings, leading to distinctions and distribution across different spaces based on the "status" a person holds. For this reason, it is necessary to educate on equality; according to Searle (Faerna, A., 2011), it is essential to raise awareness that, simply by being human, we have access to certain rights, which is why the Universal Declaration of Human Rights belongs to everyone, regardless of their social status—an aspect that every social policy should take into account.

Strict adherence to the economic condition imposed by the dominant residential model excludes sectors that cannot meet the access requirements because they lack sufficient financial solvency, or, if they have it, cannot guaranty it over time because their economies are not regularized. This is the first link in the process of violating human rights (Antón, F. & Cortés, L., 2007).

The most extreme manifestations of this problem are what we call shanty towns. That is, households living in very deficient housing conditions (without basic necessities such as electricity, water, heating, or equipment, etc.) and, in some cases, in extremely severe and risky situations (Antón, F. & Cortés, L., 2007). According to United Nations estimates, 3 billion people will live in slums by 2050. And in this context I ask... Compliance with or violation of human rights?

Today's society is built on the medieval model established over ten centuries ago, in which "marginalized" groups were forced to live on the outskirts, beyond the protection of the kingdom's walls.

It has been more than ten centuries since we have known the city as such (understanding it as a population group that is hierarchically organized and governed by a legislative framework), but really, despite the progress we have made, how much has this structure actually changed? Haven't we advanced or progressed in this regard even one iota? We find that, despite the absence of defensive walls in cities or capitals today, there is still a certain imaginary and social barrier known throughout the city (every city dweller knows where the "peripheral" or "problematic" areas are), and it is in this way that residents of these peripheries are kept apart from the city's social life. Just as in the Middle Ages, we continue to perpetuate the same value system and intolerance toward those who don't conform to "normality," forcing us to ask: Have we really progressed?

Living to pay is the reality for many families. The residential model imposed in recent years has become a negative factor in meeting housing needs and a violation of many human rights. For this reason, in this context of crisis, I wonder... Are we really free to choose, or are we puppets enslaved by our consumer society? Is the current welfare system interested in or concerned about the fulfillment of human rights?

5. CURRENT LEGISLATION ON SOCIAL PROTECTION IN SPAIN

Currently, we have the most unfair and abusive mortgage law in Europe. The Advocate General of the Court of Justice of the EU, Juliane Kokott, stated that the measures governing mortgage foreclosure proceedings in Spain "are incompatible with

European consumer protection rules.” "The mortgage law is predatory, dating back to the 19th century when mortgages were only for millionaires and aristocrats" (García Paz, 2012).

With each eviction, fundamental rights recognized in several articles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, as well as Article 47 of the 1978 Spanish Constitution, are violated; among them, the following are not being upheld:

INTERNATIONAL LEGISLATION

Articles 1 and 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), since the loss of housing entails the deprivation of the rights to liberty, security, and life. Articles 5 and 12 of the UDHR, because in the mortgage foreclosure process violations of the affected parties' private lives occur thru the repeated practice of harassing the debtor, even before the eviction is carried out, at which point both the affected parties and others who come to support them are subjected to offensive treatment.

Article 25 of the UDHR, because the rights of families are being violated, infringing the fundamental rights of the most vulnerable groups, such as minors, persons with disabilities, and the elderly.

Finally, Article 11 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights is violated, since the State is not preventing forced evictions for economic reasons, and those evicted are left completely unprotected.

NATIONAL LEGISLATION

Article 47 of the 1978 Spanish Constitution is violated, which states verbatim that "All Spaniards have the right to decent and adequate housing." Likewise, public authorities shall promote the necessary conditions and establish the relevant regulations to give effect to this right, regulating land use in accordance with the general interest to prevent speculation.

The current mortgage law in force is based on a 1946 Francoist law. Therefore, this legislation is obsolete and outdated, rendering it incapable of guaranteeing the safety of its citizens.

Another immoral piece of legislation is Law 1/2000 of January 7, 2000, on civil procedure, which condemns numerous citizens to eviction by establishing an extremely fast and short enforcement procedure that, when applied to mortgages, is highly detrimental to citizens by limiting mediation between the parties (Llopis, 2012).

Some of the measures under the autonomous communities' housing powers are aimed at boosting the production of subsidized social housing, funded by public authorities, in an effort to increase the supply of more affordable homes so that disadvantaged groups can access the market. The problem is that in recent years, the construction of subsidized housing has been a lucrative fraud, since the intended beneficiaries cannot afford it due to a lack of financial resources, while affluent middle-class households have acquired it, resulting in a completely illegal sales and rental business (Arriba González, 2009).

6. EVOLUTION OF EVICTION FIGURES IN SPAIN

Over the past few years, we have been presented with various data on the prevalence of evictions, although no source has provided reliable, precise, and detailed statistics on the magnitude of the problem. Because in our country, the official figures on the scope of this issue will not be made public by the National Statistics Institute (INE) until 2014.

The first figures were presented by the General Council of the Judiciary (2013), but they suffered from the problem that the data mixed evictions of all kinds—tenants evicted for non-payment of rent, second homes, foreigners returning to their home countries and leaving their apartments vacant, real estate developments seized from the debtor company, and court cases that ultimately ended in an agreement—which distorted reality and obscured the true picture.

What is clear, however, is the tragedy of this situation, since in 2012 alone evictions grew by 134%, totaling 526 per day in the second quarter of that year. 2012, according to data from the CGPJ (2013). The Association of Those Affected by Foreclosures and Auctions, based on statistics from the General Council of the Judiciary, reports that more than 510,000 families will lose their homes between 2008 and 2015 (Vaquero, 2012). The worst part is that the rights of our society's most vulnerable groups are being violated: 82% of foreclosed homes were the residence of at least one minor (Muñiz, 2012).

Currently, "in Spain there are about 80 evictions every day." Of these, a significant percentage affects people in vulnerable situations, even tho the law prohibits it in such cases (G. Domínguez, I., 2025).

Eviction is a serious social problem that must be addressed by the competent authorities with great urgency, not least because the right to housing is one of the principles enshrined in the Constitution as legitimate for every citizen. It is essential to

recognize that the absence of rigorous statistics contributes to the emergence of new social problems. In this context, far from addressing the challenge of halting the advance of exclusion, Spain is dismantling social protection systems, violating both the international human rights treaties it has ratified and its own Constitution.

Hence the need to demand that our democratic state governed by the rule of law publish reliable data, so that we can develop new intervention strategies.

7. SITUATION OF EVICTIONS AND EXCLUSION RESIDENTIAL EXCLUSION IN SPAIN

Throughout history, housing has been recognized as a place of residence, a physical space in which to live and develop as individuals, linked to family, a sense of belonging, protection, identity, well-being, security, shelter, and attachment. Currently, this conception is biased by the dynamics of the current real estate market (Provivienda, 2025).

Housing plays a fundamental role in the development and social integration of every individual, provided that it meets the minimum requirements and conditions of habitability, affordability, accessibility, security, and enjoyment—in other words, housing adapted to each family’s needs (Provivienda, 2023).

According to a study by the Rental Observatory (2025), residential exclusion affects 8.5 million people in Spain, impacting not only those living on the streets but also those subsisting in undignified conditions or in insecure housing (squatted properties, temporary accommodations, etc.), in overcrowded situations, or in dwellings that do not meet the minimum requirements for personal well-being, such as shacks, storage rooms, or garages, reflecting a housing emergency exacerbated by the continuous rise in both rental and purchase prices, as well as an increasingly scarce supply due to the conversion of a large portion of housing into tourist apartments (Bermejo, I., 2025).

Gráfico 1. Evolución de la exclusión residencial en España. 2011-2023⁴⁴

Graph extracted from the Provivienda report (2025)

Likewise, access to decent housing has become one of the greatest social and economic challenges in Spain in 2025. According to a report published by Provivienda (2023): “Housing vulnerability has skyrocketed, even affecting segments of the population who, until a few years ago, could afford to pay rent or meet mortgage payments without risk of exclusion, placing an excessive burden on most Spanish households” (CN construnews, 2025).

Gráfico 6. Porcentaje de hogares con sobre esfuerzo económico con todos los gastos en vivienda (todos hogares) por CCAA y variación interanual. (2023)

Graph extracted from CN construnews (2025).

On the other hand, according to the latest report presented by Provivienda (2025): “in recent years, residential exclusion has been concentrated in certain households and geographic areas, affecting low-income households with little savings capacity—such as young people and foreign-born residents—more intensely.” By geographic area, the greatest difficulties occur in regions with the most dynamic economic and tourism activity, because the process of city gentrification is causing a profound transformation in both the urban structure of cities and in local culture and sense of belonging. The proliferation of tourist accommodation and tourism-oriented services has altered the lifestyle of resident communities, prioritizing the visitor experience over the quality of life of local inhabitants. This phenomenon directly affects the original population, made up of middle-class and/or more vulnerable sectors, who are gradually displaced due to rising housing prices, the overall cost of living, and the loss of cultural identity and local belonging” (Provivienda, 2025),

Gráfico 7. Evolución comparada de los salarios medios, la renta media de los hogares no propietarios y los precios de venta y alquiler de una vivienda en España. 2011-2024.

Graph extracted from the Provivienda report (2025)

For these reasons, it is essential that institutions and the public administration continue to strengthen a more robust, secure, transparent, and stable housing provision system that guarantees access to housing as a fundamental and non-negotiable right, regardless of real estate market fluctuations and interests (Provivienda, 2025). Hence the importance of developing new public policies to help mitigate this situation and address the current housing crisis that our country has been experiencing in recent years.

8. RECENT EVOLUTION OF EVICTIONS

According to the newspaper El País (2025), a total of 27,564 evictions were recorded in Spain in 2024, representing a 3.4% increase compared to the previous year (EP, 2025).

Of all those evictions or forced expropriations, approximately 75% were due to unpaid rent, while only 18.4% resulted from mortgage foreclosures (Fábrega, J. 2024). This trend continued throughout the first quarter of 2025, with 77% of evictions linked to rent arrears (Aranda, J.L., 2025).

Own elaboration based on data from EpData (2025). Autonomous Communities Most Affected

According to the newspaper El País (2025), the autonomous communities in Spain with the highest number of evictions in 2024 were Catalonia (7,381 cases), Andalusia (4,027), and the Valencian Community (3,610) (EP, 2025). However, when the

phenomenon is analyzed on a per capita basis, the Balearic and Canary Islands have the highest rates due to tourism pressure and rising rents (Aranda, J. L., 2025). In Madrid, an estimated six evictions occur daily, with a 13% increase in 2024 (García, J. & Marcos, J., 2025), and Catalonia leads evictions in Spain: more than 20 per day (Marchena, D., 2025).

Own elaboration based on data extracted from El País (2025).

ANALYSIS OF RESIDENTIAL EXCLUSION IN SPAIN (2012–2025)

Currently, in our country, residential exclusion has become a persistent problem over the past decade, reflecting both the impact of the economic crisis and the ineffectiveness of current public policies on public and social housing.

In 2012, approximately 8.5 million people lived in Conditions of residential exclusion. This figure included situations of thousands of homeless people, unsafe or uninhabitable housing, and overcrowding. The trend was upward, reaching a peak in 2021 with nearly 11 million people affected, representing approximately 23.7% of the population, according to Fundación FOESSA (2024). From that point onward, there was a progressive decline in 2024, when the number fell to 9.4 million, equivalent to approximately 20% of households. However, in 2025, estimates indicate a return to figures similar to those of 2012, with 8.5 million people affected, suggesting a degree of stabilization, albeit far from a definitive solution (Fundación FOESSA, 2024).

This evolution shows how the various economic crises our country has endured for many years intensified the problem, while recovery efforts and government measures have contributed to only a partial reduction, proving ineffective or insufficient to resolve and address this situation. The persistence of these high figures reveals that access to housing has become a structural issue of social protection within our current welfare system, which our government must confront and attempt to resolve as quickly as possible

to prevent the situation from worsening or becoming entrenched over time. Analysis of Residential Exclusion in Spain (2012–2025)

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Likewise, the National Statistics Institute (INE, 2024) estimates that 25.8% of the Spanish population is at risk of poverty or social exclusion, while 8.3% suffers severe material and social deprivation. In particular, 35% of lower-income households have struggled to meet housing-related payments since the pandemic (FEANTSA, 2021), which is why residential exclusion and evictions have resurfaced after several years of decline or reduced social impact among the population.

Below is a scatter plot that visually presents the entire analysis presented above:

Own elaboration based on data extracted from the FOESSA Foundation (2024).

8. GOVERNMENT OF SPAIN'S ACTIONS IN RESPONSE TO THIS ISSUE ACTIONS BY THE GOVERNMENT OF SPAIN IN RESPONSE TO THIS ISSUE

Our current government has adopted several relevant measures (although with insufficient results) to mitigate the current situation of housing exclusion: 1. The current government has adopted several relevant measures (although with insufficient results) to mitigate the current situation of housing exclusion: Law 12/2023 on the Right to Housing includes measures such as rent price caps, controls on large landlords, and the suspension of evictions in vulnerable situations (Government of Spain, 2023).

2. Law 12/2023 on the Right to Housing includes measures such as rent caps, controls on large landlords, and the suspension of evictions in vulnerable situations (Government of Spain, 2023). 2. A PERTE (Strategic Project for Economic Recovery and

Transformation) for industrialized housing has been launched, with an investment of €1.3 billion to build between 15,000 and 20,000 homes annually (Wikipedia, 2025). A PERTE (Strategic Project for Economic Recovery and Transformation) for industrialized housing has been launched, with an investment of €1.3 billion to build between 15,000 and 20,000 homes annually (Wikipedia, 2025).

3. In the case of Madrid, the regional government carried out 121 evictions from social housing in 2024 (the highest number in a decade), linked to its anti-squatting policy (Fernández P., 2025). In the case of Madrid, the regional government carried out 121 evictions from social housing in 2024 (the highest figure in a decade), linked to its antisquatter policy (Fernández P. 2025).

9. RECOMMENDATIONS AND PRESSURE FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Over the past few months, the European Commission has warned at the UN that Spain only has 1.5% public housing, compared to the European average of 9%. Consequently, it has recommended tripling this figure, reforming the Land Law, expediting building permits, and curbing the tourist rental market (European Commission, 2025).

For their part, European organizations such as FEANTSA, EAPN, and ESPN have called on Member States to improve oversight of evictions and forced expropriations, strive to guaranty housing alternatives, and strengthen access to affordable housing (EAPN España, 2024).

14. SPANISH MORTGAGE LAW COMPARED TO OTHER COUNTRIES

SPANISH MORTGAGE LAW COMPARED TO OTHER COUNTRIES

Today, according to the National Housing Observatory, “the price of used housing in Spain rose by 14.7% last July compared to the previous year, reaching an average of 2,471 euros per square meter.” (Agencies, 2025), reflecting a significant imbalance between housing supply and demand, driving rental and purchase prices to exorbitant levels. Hence, housing is the primary concern of most Spaniards, according to the CIS (Martínez, E. & Palacios, L., 2025). Likewise, according to data collected by the Housing Observatory (2025) and extracted from the INE, at the end of the last quarter housing prices in Spain rose again, reaching their highest level in the past 18 years.

Source: INE 2025.

Currently, the rise in housing prices in Spain reflects a symptom of a structural problem that threatens to undermine social cohesion and well-being and requires urgent

intervention due to the social emergency it is causing. During the first quarter of this year, housing prices in Spain grew twice as fast as in the rest of Europe, with real estate values in the country up 12.3% compared to 5.7% across the European Union, turning a constitutional right into a “right” governed by the logic of a speculative market (as seen in vulture funds and residential properties converted into tourist businesses) (Martínez, M., 2025).

And indeed, our current real estate legislation is proving insufficient to address the situation in a country with one of the lowest rates of public housing construction in Europe and at the forefront of a growing price surge, primarily due to underinvestment in social housing, a legal framework that favors speculation, and excessive short-term tourism that has displaced residents and left them without housing options (Martínez, M., 2025), driving up prices and requirements for renting or buying a home to an excessive degree. And, as we have mentioned throughout this article, our current mortgage law is not viable; therefore, it is necessary to seek alternatives that address this issue. Hence the importance of examining the various options available in our environment in order to identify which measures could be feasible in Spain.

15. PSYCHOLOGICAL CONSEQUENCES OF AN EVICTION PROCESS ON THE INDIVIDUAL

Nowadays, no one doubts the social function of housing, as it is part of our identity, providing us with security, protection, privacy... Housing is a central element in people's lives; it is a fundamental right, like education, healthcare, and social protection... It is where we learn to relate to one another, where our personality is first structured, and where we feel identified with a specific space and territory. Therefore, the relationship between social exclusion and residential exclusion can be affirmed, because residential exclusion is not limited to the perpetuation of shantytowns and substandard housing, but also encompasses families' difficulties in accessing better-equipped housing, overcrowding and over-occupancy in some homes, and physical and economic maintenance challenges, which in some cases also affect public rental housing (Antón and Cortés, 2007). Housing plays a fundamental role in social organization and provides social stability in our society; therefore, becoming homeless creates a gap on the social, psychological, and physical levels (coronary problems, intestinal issues, etc.). According to Cortés and Ramis (2013), the eviction process brings with it the development of psychological disorders such as Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder, Affective Disorder (depression), sleep disorders, anxiety

disorders, and even personality disorders in children. Throughout the process, the person is psychologically overwhelmed, experiencing feelings such as shame, fear, failure, helplessness, worry, frustration, anger, guilt, uncertainty, and sadness. These feelings not only lead to the loss of relationships but also to the loss of personal identity, because undergoing an eviction process can trigger social disintegration, resulting in social exclusion or, in the worst cases, suicide, since anyone under stress or great suffering may resort to unthinkable actions, and “behind every eviction there are people, families, experiences, and dreams turned into the worst nightmare” (Alemany and Colau, 2012). Furthermore, the violation of the right to housing entails the infringement of other rights, such as the right to health, since the anxiety caused by impending eviction leads to severe psychological disorders that manifest as violence, drug use, mental illness, family tensions, and even suicide attempts.

Until the crisis began, suicide, like evictions, had become a secondary, hidden issue, but in recent years many cases have appeared in the media, reporting on suicides linked to the pressure stemming from over-indebtedness and the resulting loss of the family home. “In 2012 alone, it is estimated that 119 people committed suicide, unable to overcome the powerlessness of watching their families’ lives being ‘destroyed’” (Delgado, 2012). As we can see, some sources show a clear relationship between suicides and evictions, while others deny it: “Psychiatry experts assert that a direct link between suicides and evictions cannot be established” (EITB, 2013), as Manuel Gómez Beneyto says. Although statistics do not reflect an increase in suicide rates in Spain, the relationship between eviction and suicide is evident; the reason this issue is not reflected in the data is that the number of suicides related to evictions is only one or two dozen, so the figures are not affected. However, the very existence of this rate is a clear indicator that this legislation increases the number of suicides (Ferro, L., 2013).

It is important to publish official data on this issue because by making it invisible, society is prevented from recognizing the gravity of the situation, thereby absolving those responsible of their accountability. Well, these feelings of helplessness, failure, demotivation, anger, and powerlessness generated by the crisis situation destroy all cohesion, producing an enormous social fracture. Likewise, beyond the figures, there are many cases that have demonstrated the link between suicides and evictions, illustrating the dehumanization inherent in our current capitalist society.

16. THE DIFFICULTIES FACED BY THE SPANISH POPULATION IN DIFFICULTIES FACED BY THE SPANISH POPULATION IN ACCESS TO DECENT HOUSING

Today, access to decent housing has become one of the main socioeconomic challenges to address in our current welfare system, because despite the fact that the Spanish Constitution, in Article 47, recognizes the right of all citizens to enjoy decent housing, the reality is that under our current system or real estate market it is a dream that very few people are able to attain and enjoy. Over the past few decades, the rising costs of buying and renting property, coupled with job insecurity and a limited supply of public housing, have created an especially adverse environment, significantly affecting both families and younger people.

For many families, housing represents the largest household expense, leading to situations of over-indebtedness or the inability to cover other basic needs. According to data from the National Institute of Statistics (INE, 2023), more than 30% of households spend at least 40% of their income on housing, which in most cases leads to an enormous emotional burden for anyone.

This situation is exacerbated among the younger population, where Spain's emancipation rate is one of the lowest and most delayed in all of Europe, according to the Spanish Youth Council (CJE, 2023). In 2023, the average age of emancipation stood at around 30 years, a fairly high figure compared to the average age of emancipation for young Europeans—almost four years above the EU average of approximately 26 years (Mena, M., 2023)—and it is that instability, precariousness, scarcity, and temporary employment, as well as low wages, make it difficult to access the housing market, especially in large cities, where prices are completely disproportionate to the average income of young people. This situation not only delays their independence but also limits their personal development, their ability to start a family, and their full participation in economic and social life.

Consequently, the lack of effective public policies aimed at affordable housing—such as increasing the construction of social housing, regulating the rental market (which currently directs the real estate market toward lucrative tourist rentals, failing to ensure or regulate a fair market oriented toward people's quality of life and social welfare), the absence of direct financial support for vulnerable groups or those facing greater barriers to access, and the insufficient housing supply to meet such high demand and need—

perpetuates and promotes a completely unequal and unjust model that hinders and prevents social cohesion and well-being by undermining the right to housing, a basic constitutional right essential for every individual.

10. IN CONCLUSION

Since the birth of the State, citizens have been willing to exchange part of their freedom or rights for the protection provided by our welfare state. The problem is that today we see our freedom and rights curtailed in exchange for nothing, since the majority of the population is left unprotected by the system. This is an injustice, for, as Hegel denounced, the individual should not be abandoned by the system; rather, the State should provide support that guides them toward the pursuit of their individual interests while maintaining social cohesion. Therefore, it is necessary to create a state whose rulers trust in and promote values that guide us toward a just and egalitarian world, because in this crisis of values the role of education is fundamental.

Let us recall that even in ancient Greece, its inhabitants were educated from childhood to be good citizens, with an emphasis on the importance of each individual fighting to defend the common good, since, as Kant (1978) pointed out, human actions, although determined by reason, are influenced by certain “inclinations” such as hatred, corruption, greed, etc., which can corrupt the individual.

Today, our politicians have drifted away from the essence of their democratic role, becoming mere puppets in the hands of an unscrupulous market, forgetting that true democracy is one in which power resides in the people. Hence the importance of education to raise public awareness of the need to implement a political framework that guarantees and promotes human rights within our current welfare system. Currently, access to housing, understood as a human right, constitutes a key element for human dignity and the empowerment of citizens, based on the hypothesis that human rights are universal and the authorities are responsible for providing this right to all individuals without distinction, hence the need for current public policies to take into account the current Declaration of Human Rights (Dede, G. 2007).

Today, the violation of the right to housing is not only suffered by the most disadvantaged sectors of the population, but also affects the formerly so-called “middle class,” since even having an open-ended employment contract does not guarantee access to decent housing, demonstrating the enormous scale of the problem that public authorities should address with the utmost urgency.

As we can see, thousands of citizens have their rights violated every day; for this reason, it is necessary not only to educate in values but also to raise public awareness of the universal essence of the human being, sensitizing society to the need for all of humanity to adopt a new morality, a new ethic shared globally thru universal norms such as the current Declaration of Human Rights, because, as he reminded us, Kant (1978) argued that man has come into the world to introduce a new moral value, replacing being with ought-to-be.

To conclude this reflective article, I would like to recall how, at present, an indebted natural person is entirely unprotected under our current legal system—a situation that, given the way our housing system or model is presented to the public, could affect any citizen, preventing them from accessing decent housing or, in the worst case, even losing it, resulting in evictions or forced expropriations.

Housing, like healthcare or education, is a right, but it has not been protected in the same way as other social rights; it is a right that remains pending. Housing facilitates access to other rights, such as employment, healthcare, education, etc. In other words, housing can be a key factor in a person's integration, or, conversely, lacking housing or living in inadequate conditions can trigger processes of marginalization and social exclusion. Hence the need to assess the various alternatives available in our immediate surroundings. It is necessary to replace the morality of guilt, as Nietzsche denounced in "On the Genealogy of Morality" (1996), with an ethics of human rights, because justice can be extended to all peoples of the world by promoting policies that take human rights into account, since only in this way will we contribute to the strengthening of citizenship and the birth of a real and representative democracy, because... Is it really impossible to fulfill the current Universal Declaration of Human Rights, as well as a right recognized by the Spanish Constitution today? Is access to decent housing guaranteed for everyone today? Are we free to access decent housing on equal terms?

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